

Acknowledgments

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First report of narrow brown leaf spot disease of rice in West Bengal, India

A. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, West Bengal, India

During the 2001 wet season (Jun–Nov), the popular, high-yielding, and widely adapted cultivar Swarna was observed to have many linear red-brown spots. These had light-colored margins and light brown to gray centers. Observed on leaves during the later (dough and mature grain) growth stages, the spots were restricted between the veins. The experimental plots of the rice-wheat system of the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, were exposed to these weather conditions: mean maximum temperature, 32 °C; mean minimum temperature, 25 °C; relative humidity, 98%; and rainfall, 942 mm. A similar type of lesions was also found on the leaf sheaths, pedicels, and glumes. The lesions were 2–10 × 0.5–1 mm and they coalesced to form long, threadlike

brown lesions parallel to the veins on the entire leaves.

A preliminary microscopic study of the 20-d-old fungal colony revealed that the conidiophores emerge from host stomata; are pale brown, geniculate, in clusters of 3–5, and uniform in color; have three or more septa; are irregular in width and have rounded tips; and the old scarps are rounded on conspicuous shoulders or on short peg-like protrusions, measuring 80–140 × 4–6 mm. Conidia were light olive and cylindrical to subclavate, with 3–10 septa, an obovate base, blunt tips, in whorls of 3–4 on the conidiophore tip and measuring 15–60 × 3–5 mm. Conidia produced in rice-straw agar-culture media were hyaline. These confirmed that the fungus is *Cercospora janseana* (Racib.) O.

Const. and it causes narrow brown leaf spot (NBLS) or cercospora leaf spot disease.

Pathogenicity tests were done on Swarna during panicle emergence. The plants were sprayed with spore suspension (8×10^4 spores mL⁻¹ water) in late afternoon, then covered with a polythene sheet to preserve the moisture. The plants were surface-irrigated profusely by using tube-well water. Typical NBLS symptoms appeared within 21–25 d after inoculation. This is the first report of this disease from the state of West Bengal, India.

The affected leaf area was only 5%. As such, the incidence was not considered to be serious but close monitoring is necessary to prevent its spread.

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